

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON DEVELOPMENTS IN EDUCATION

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The conference will start at 14:00 on the Zoom platform.

Moderator: Subash Gupta

Speakers

Tea Mchedluri –Education in new life.

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Tsisana Kolotadze- Biological sciences in real life.

Iakob Gogebashvili Telavi State University, Georgia. Kartuli University Street 1, Telavi, E-mail: Cisana.kolotadze@tesau.edu.ge

Lika.Mosemgvdlishvili - Practice of eastern thinkers

Iakob Gogebashvili Telavi State University, Georgia. Kartuli University Street 1, Telavi, E-mail: Lika.mosemgvdlishvili@tesau.edu.ge

Tamar Noniashvili- Students linguistic competence

Iakob Gogebashvili Telavi State University, Georgia. Kartuli University Street 1, Telavi

Agzamova Shaira Abdusalamovna- Role of vitamin D

Professor of the Department of Family Medicine No. 1, Physical Education, Civil Defense of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Doctor of Medical Sciences

Saodat Rustamova - The management system of JSC “airways of Uzbekistan

Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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AGRICULTURE

Determination of the residual amount of calcium and magnesium in the soil after use of mineral fertilizers in viticulture

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Azerbaijan is the center of the emergence and formation of the culture of grapes, an ancient focus of viticulture and winemaking. Not only do numerous literary data testify to the age of cultivation of grapes in Azerbaijan, but also the monuments of material culture found in archeological excavations, tools used for growing grapes and preparing wine, pottery with deposits of tartar on the walls, as well as seeds, leaves and some other parts of the grape plant. Most fertilizers that are commonly used in viticulture contain the three basic plant nutrients: nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. Some fertilizers also contain certain "micronutrients," such as zinc and other metals, that are necessary for plant growth. Materials that are applied to the land primarily to enhance soil characteristics (rather than as plant food) are commonly referred to as soil amendments. **Fertilizer**, natural or artificial substance containing the chemical elements that improve growth and productiveness of plants. It is known that, use of mineral or organic fertilizers in agriculture increases inputs of nutrients to soils, and the form in which the nutrients are applied and their fate in the soil-plant system determine the overall effects on soil pH. Soil acidification is a widespread natural phenomenon in regions with medium to high rainfall, and agricultural production systems can accelerate soil acidification processes through perturbation of the natural cycles of calcium, magnesium, iron and zinc in soil. Fertilizers are very valuable, as they replace the soil nutrients used up by plants. The three primary soil nutrients often in short supply are potassium, phosphorous and nitrogen (NPK) compounds. These are commonly referred to as macronutrients. Certain other elements like boron, zinc and manganese are necessary in extremely small amounts and are known as micronutrients.

The sample for analysis is the soil from ground under the grape variety Tabrizi (white), which was selected from the GoyGol District. A chemical analysis of soil

samples was carried out with different methods. Calcium and magnesium was determinate with A.Asetat-AAS method.

Table. The sample for analysis is the soil under grape variety of Tabrizi

Elements	Norm	Results	Appraisal
Calcium	1150-3500 ppm	4460,00	high
Magnezium	160-480ppm	585,30	high

As can be seen from the table, the amount of calcium and magnesium is high due to excessive uses of mineral fertilizers.

Key words: analysis, grape, fertilizers, viticulture, amount, variety.

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Species structure and incidence of registration of surgical diseases of the distal extremities in cows

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In recent years, significant structural changes have occurred in dairy cattle breeding and other livestock industries, that is, there has been a tendency to increase the number of livestock due to reproduction and purchase of imported young animals, characterized by high milk productivity, but relatively low physiological and biochemical stability due to genetic features - reduced immunity due to high energy metabolism and increased stress-sensitivity to negative factors, therefore, the service life of highly productive cows is insignificant. Among surgical diseases of cattle of dairy and fattening complexes, 80-90% are occupied by purulent–necrotic processes in the area of the fingers, of which ulcers and pododermatitis are most common, to a lesser extent - subacute with a predominance of purulent-necrotic processes and a tendency to various complications (corolla phlegmon, purulent arthritis and panarthritis of the hoof and crown joints, necrosis of finger bones and tendons).

It was found that the pelvic extremities are most often affected – 80,46%, and in 61,33% of cases the process is localized in the area of the third finger. Inflammatory processes of the base of the hoof skin – pododermatitis often occur (up to 62% of all registered patients with limb lesions). Cattle are mass-produced in many farms of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The purpose of the study is to study the species structure and incidence of registration of surgical diseases of the distal extremities in cows, in conditions of stable – pasture technology of maintenance.

The work was carried out in the production conditions of dairy farms of the Gay-Gelsky district with stable-pasture technology of maintenance, as well as at the Department of Obstetrics Therapy and Surgery of the ASAU.

In order to achieve this goal and solve a number of formulated scientific and practical tasks, methods of analytical study of veterinary accounting documents and reporting on the morbidity of cattle with diseases of non-infectious etiology, as well as records in the logs of registration of veterinary outpatient admission of patients were

applied. In addition, methods of general clinical examination of animals were used for the purpose of diagnosis and differential diagnosis of surgical diseases of the distal extremities in cows.

Thus, according to the results of the study of the species structure and the incidence of diagnosing surgical diseases of the distal extremities in cows in the conditions of stable-pasture technology of maintenance, it was found that their distribution is equal to 29,46% of the total number of examined animals in the amount of 784 heads, the bulk are crumb wounds – 16,88%; crumb ulcers – 16,45%; pododermatitis – 12,99%, with the most pronounced seasonality in the winter stall period and age-related incidence on the 3rd lactation of economically productive operation.

Key words: cow, halo wound, the wound crumb, phlegmon, pododermatitis, laminitis, ulcers crumb.

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Qualitative determination of pesticide residues in grape samples by ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography

Tagizada A.T., F.S. Mustafaeva, E.P.Orujov, Musaeva G.A.

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Key words: analysis, grapes, pesticide, viticulture, amount, variety, determination.

This study was conducted to determine pesticides residue levels in grapes samples which taken from vineyards implemented good agricultural practice in Ganja-Gazach region in 2019 growing seasons. The occurrence of pesticide residues in grapes was investigated. A targeted analysis of 4 pesticide residues in grape sample Madrasa from organic and conventional production were performed using the QuEChERS (Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged and Safe) extraction method, followed by ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry. The most commonly detected residues were fungicides (e.g., difenoconazole) and insecticides (e.g., acetamiprid). An ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography–high resolution mass spectrometry method (UHPLC–(HR)MS) was used for screening of pesticide residues. Grapes are among the most widely grown fruits in Ganja-Gazach region of Azerbaijan. The world grape production amounts about 75.8 million tons. Approximately 50% of grapes are used in wine production. The use of pesticides in grapevine production provides various benefits, the presence of pesticide residues in grapes rise health concerns. In conventional production, various plant protection products (PPP), especially fungicides and insecticides, are widely used for protecting grapevine.

The analyses of 5 pesticide residues were performed using the ultra-high-performance liquid chromatograph Waters Acquity UPLC system coupled to a triple quadrupole tandem mass spectrometer Xevo TQ-S (both Waters, Milford, MA, USA) in electrospray positive (ESI+) and negative (ESI-) modes.

This study presents the results of the analyses of pesticide residues and metabolites in grapes and wines from both conventional and organic production. Fungicides and insecticides were the most commonly detected pesticide residues; in total, residues

of 4 different pesticides residues were found in grapes respectively. Several samples contained no quantifiable residues of parent pesticides (or with their residues below the quantification limit of 0.01 mg/kg), while metabolites of such pesticides were unequivocally found. This was observed in the case of cyprodinil, acetamiprid, carbendazim and difenoconazole in grapes.

Table. The limits of quantification, MRLs and minimum and maximum concentrations of detected pesticides in tested grapes

		GRAPES			
		Concentration of Residues [mg/kg]			
Analyte (f/i) ¹	LOQ [mg/kg]	N	Minimum	Maximum	MRL ²
acetamiprid (i)	0.001	2	0.077	0.136	0.5
carbendazim (f)	0.001	0	0	0	0.4
cyprodinil (f)	0.001	4	0.010	0.300	3
difenoconazole (f)	0.001	2	0.001	0.003	3

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HISTORY

The Cold War: an ideological conflict

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Supervisor: Iakob Gogebashvili Telavi State University, Associate Professor
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Abstract: The Cold War was a conflict of competing ideologies, which consumed global politics throughout the 20th century. While it was ostensibly fought between the Soviet Union and the United States of America, the rest of the world was also forced to pick sides in this clash of superpowers. While weapons of mass destruction were stockpiled on both sides, many small wars were fought worldwide. This international conflict brought mankind to the brink and its impact is still being felt today.

Introduction: As the second World War drew to a close, the western powers no longer needed to ally themselves with the communist juggernaut, and relations turned frosty. As the allies marched towards Berlin in the eleventh hour of the conflict, it was obvious that control of post-war Europe was hanging in the balance. Germany itself was soon occupied by the Russians, the Americans, the French, and the British. Control of Berlin became the first flashpoint of the Cold War, as the Americans were reluctant to cooperate with the Russians, who were attempting to catch escaping Germans fleeing west to avoid them. Germany and the USSR had fought a particularly ruthless war, and many Germans were terrified of the treatment they were likely to receive in Soviet hands. While the western powers were determined to aid the Germans and install an independent government as soon as possible, Stalin immediately turned East Germany into a satellite state and plotted to oust the rest of the Allies. By June of 1948, the Soviets had introduced a blockade in Berlin, cutting off roads, railways, and lines of communication, in an attempt to starve American-held West Berlin into submission.

In response, the Western Powers took to the skies, dropping 13,000 tons of supplies from the air, in an event known as the Berlin Airlift. The USSR was ultimately

forced to lift the blockade in 1949, but Berlin remained split down the middle, and it would stay that way until 1989. Across the rest of Europe, most western soldiers had gone home after Germany was defeated, but troops from the USSR never left eastern Europe. Soon, they installed pro-communist governments in many neighboring countries. The staggering onslaught of Soviet domination led British Prime Minister Winston Churchill to remark that an “iron curtain” had descended across the continent.

Tensions were high and the soviets soon successfully field-tested their own nuclear bomb in 1949. To protect themselves against the new enormous communist bloc, the western powers formed, an alliance by founding NATO, the North Atlantic Treaty Organization. A few years later, in 1955, the Eastern Bloc countries would sign the Warsaw pact, forming a coherent alliance of their own. As communism continued to spread across the globe, the Cold War began with a series of proxy wars fought in many different countries. Asia, soon became a major theater of war in the ideological battle between communism and the capitalist West. The defeat of Japan in World War Two had led to a major power vacuum in the region, causing chaos in several countries. In China, the country’s nationalist army, led by Chiang Kai-Shek, was seriously weakened after fighting the Japanese, which gave the communists rebels, led by Mao Zedong, an advantage in civil war. The communists quickly won control of China in 1949, while the remaining nationalists were forced to flee to Taiwan, a territory still disputed to this day. Meanwhile, in nearby Korea, the country was split in half at the end of World War Two by Soviet and western troops who divided the country along the 38th parallel. Emboldened by Communist successes in China, the Communist North invaded the South, causing the US and 14 other western countries to send troops to support Seoul’s government. The bloody conflict was complex and would end in a total stalemate by 1953. The same year, the ferocious Soviet Premier, Joseph Stalin, finally died, leading to a government policy shift in the USSR.

The new Soviet leader, Nikita Khrushchev, had been quietly critical of Stalin and he soon became one of the USSR most energetic and competent leaders. Under his tenure, the USSR would see a massive wave of technological change in a push to fight the culture war against the highly influential United States. One of Khrushchev's key achievements was pushing ahead in the Space Race, a technological war between the US and the USSR. The Space Race was fueled by early advances in rocketry that had taken place in Nazi Germany. After the war, both the Soviets and the Americans seized as much information as possible from German scientists. The Americans promised to "forget" any war crimes committed by Germans who worked for them while the Soviets simply kidnapped scientists when they found them. While initially the Soviets were used this stolen information to make missiles, when Khrushchev heard that the Americans were working on putting a satellite into space, he immediately created the Soviet Space Program. The Soviets would launch their first satellite, Sputnik one in 1957, infuriating the Americans who didn't launch their satellite, Explorer One, until 1958. While the Americans created the National Aeronautics and Space Administration -NASA- in 1960, the Soviets would continue to take the lead in the Space Race for quite some time, getting the first man Yuri Gagarin, into space in 1961. The race between two powers to improve technology would lead to many serious accidents, as poorly tested equipment was used too early by both sides. Eventually, as Soviet progress slowed down in the late 60s under the new Soviet Premier Brezhnev, the Americans pulled ahead, landing on the moon in 1969. The early 60s represented not only the peak of the Space Race, it was the absolute peak of cold War tension-the Cuban Missile Crisis.

In the 50s, the small Caribbean country of Cuba had long been overdue a regime change and was experiencing severe social unrest. Still, the US was concerned that any overthrow of the ruling dictator, Batista, would result in a communist government. When the rebel guerrillas, led by Fidel Castro, took over Havana, America was extremely concerned. In 1961, the US launched the Bay of Pigs Invasion to remove Castro, but it soon backfired. The attack failed, and Cuba

responded by definitively siding with the USSR and officially declaring itself communists. With Cuba on their side, the USSR moved some of its missiles to the island in 1962, when Americans got wind of this, a nail-bitingly tense stand-off ensued. President Kennedy responded with a live TV broadcast, during which he declared that if Cuba fired at the US, the US would fire at the USSR, plunging the world into an all-out nuclear war. The world held its breath as negotiations between the two powers continued. Eventually, it was agreed that the USSR would remove its weapons if the US did likewise, dismantling key missile sites in nearby Turkey. Today the Cuban Missile Crisis is still the closest the world has ever gotten to a world-ending nuclear cataclysm. To halt the spread of communism, America would get involved in many more nations' politics, just it had with Cuba. The US forced regime change in several Latin American nations throughout the 20th century, including Guatemala in 1954 and Grenada in 1983. President Lyndon B. Johnson also invaded the Dominican Republic in 1965 to prevent a communist dictatorship from arising when the country was experiencing political turmoil. President Johnson would gain a reputation as something of a war hawk during the Cold War, and he is famous for his involvement in the bloodiest of all the Cold War conflicts-Vietnam. Vietnam was in much the same situation that Korea had been in, split between an American-allied South and communist North. Still, while America had initially been relatively hands-off about the conflict, by the-mid 60s, it seemed as though the South would lose. In response to a series of attacks on the American military, President Johnson okayed the bombing of Vietnam in Operation Rolling Thunder before sending many more American soldiers to the country in the summer of 1965. The Vietnam war would become a humanitarian disaster, and it is still grimly remembered today for the extreme psychological damage it caused to those who fought in the conflict. Throughout the war, the Vietnamese communists used guerrilla tactics, taking advantage of the Vietnamese jungle to ambush the Americans at every opportunity. American soldiers often struggled to find the rebel Viet Cong or differentiate between them and their local allies. As the country celebrated lunar

New Year in 1968, communists' forces launched a way of surprise attacks known as the Tet Offensive. In response, the Americans resorted to using napalm to flatten whole villages in a deadly rain of fire. After the Tet Offensive, a string of dramatic attacks carried out by the North Vietnamese, America's anti-war protests became deafeningly loud. American troops were increasingly removed from the country, hoping that the well-trained South Vietnamese would take over the fight. US President Nixon's government would intensify the bombing of Vietnam in the 1970s. The communists North and the Viet Cong would ultimately wipe out all resistance on the ground by 1975, bringing the hugely unpopular conflict to a close.

During the 70s, Cold War tensions eased slightly, as a desire for peace and security on both sides led to series of talks known as SALT, or the strategic Arms Limitation Talks. These diplomatic discussions aimed to get both the US and USSR to reduce the number of missiles they had on hand. President Nixon also opens up diplomatic relations with China in 1972. Despite being communist, the Chinese government did not see eye-to-eye with the Soviet Union and they were happy to forge a new business relationship with America. While it seemed as though the conflict was cooling down, in 1979, the Soviet Union took the dramatic step of invading Afghanistan to support the communist coup that had broken out there.

The new disarmament deal, known as SALT II, soon collapsed, and the US responded by founding and supplying various rebel groups in the region, including extremist Islamic militias. By 1980 the election of Ronald Reagan had pushed Cold War politics to a fevered pitch once more. Reagan used fiery, bellicose language to describe the Soviet Union, and he ramped up the rhetoric about America's War against the "Eviler Empire." Reagan's return to Cold War paranoia was deeply polarizing, but he ultimately lived to see the USSR dismantled, which made him extremely popular with any people. Fortunately for Reagan, Mikhail Gorbachev became Soviet premier in 1985. Gorbachev was from a young generation, fed up with the lack of material progress the Soviet Union was making. The Soviets spent almost 30% of their budget on their military and breadlines. A lack of technological

progress over the previous two decades meant that the USSR's living standards were dramatically worse than in the West. By way of a solution, in the late 80s, Gorbachev introduced a series of reforms, known as Glasnost and Perestroika. He hoped to democratize the USSR, allow more free movement, free information, and access to more economic markets in a bid to improve living conditions for the Soviet people. Small private business enterprises were suddenly permitted to re-introduce market competition, and the press was finally allowed to print criticism of the administration.

Conclusion: As free elections were slowly introduced across many levels of government, it became apparent that Gorbachev had created his own undoing. While Gorbachev sought to reform the USSR, he did not realize that he would ultimately destroy it. Countries that had absorbed by the USSR long ago, such as Latvia and Lithuania, quickly stormed independence movements. When free movement was announced between East and West Berlin, a crowd of locals smashed the Berlin Wall to pieces, after decades of division. The USSR's Eastern Bloc allies, including Poland, Czechoslovakia, Romania, Hungary, Albania and Bulgaria, all threw out their communist governments during a spectacular wave of popular revolts in 1988-81. Gorbachev's uneasy compromise between a communist system and a free-market economy began causing chaos, as many people wanted to embrace western-style capitalism as soon as possible. Gorbachev was soon ousted when Boris Yeltsin was elected Russian president in 1991. Yeltsin banned the communist party, demanded more reforms, and allowed many countries to break away from Russia. During 1991, the Soviet Union officially dissolved, and many democratic nations emerged from the rubble. The Cold War was finally over.

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MEDICINE

Benefits of Newly Developed Virtual Patient Simulation Software

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Abstract

Currently, medical simulation education, in particular virtual patient electronic platforms, is used as an effective method of teaching students, as well as performing various tasks. Simulation technologies help the student to acquire knowledge and master practical skills. Virtual patient systems display clinical scenarios on a digital screen and act like a human, with the help of a real actor. The created virtual electronic platform of the patient helps the student to test his knowledge, master practical skills and learn remotely using digital scenarios.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, our lifestyles have become even more dependent on the online lifestyle. This pandemic has seriously affected students studying in medical universities. After the transition of education to the online process of students, their interaction with the patient seriously hindered the development of their practical skills and competencies in treatment. This will have a negative impact on the training of qualified and professional personnel in the future.

Based on the above, the main goal was to create virtual patient software and study its effectiveness.

In 2011, Robin et al. expressed the opinion that the transition to the use of teaching technologies in medical education and their adoption would give a good result. They encouraged the adoption and use of technology as a means of enhancing the student experience and called for funding and leadership support to create the necessary infrastructure and appropriate use of such technologies. This type of platform is particularly suitable for training and facilitating collaborative teamwork.

The created by us platform was financed by the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan within the framework of the grant

project and it is planned to be presented to users not only in Uzbek, but also in English, Russian and other languages.

Keywords: virtual patient, simulation training, e-learning platform, medical education technologies.

Hematological and biochemical status of the cats after ovariectomy various operating accesses

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The work was performed at the Department of Obstetrics and Surgery Therapy of ASAU. The object of the study was cats of different age and breed groups who were admitted to an outpatient appointment with indications for ovariectomy, from among which two experimental groups of animal analogues of 5 heads each were formed. In the first, after preliminary preparation of the surgical field, surgical access was performed using an incision of the abdominal wall in the pre-umbilical region, i.e., along the white line of the abdomen. In the second experimental group, the operation was performed by lateral access, i.e., the incision was made in the middle between the mukluk and the last rib. Throughout the study (before sterilization, on the 3rd, 7th and 10th days), blood was taken from the animals for biochemical and hematological analyses. The biomaterial was taken from the safe vein into test tubes with a coagulation activator. The cytomorphological composition of whole blood was studied using an automatic hematological analyzer "Abacus vet 10". Biochemical analysis was performed on an automatic analyzer Vet test.

During ovariectomy along the white line of the abdomen in cats of the first experimental group, there were 9.52% more erythrocytes in the vascular bed, 4,38% more platelets, 10,01% fewer granulocytes, 27,36% fewer monocytes, 5,05% lymphocytes, compared with animal analogues from the second experimental group, in which extirpation ovaries were carried out by lateral access.

In the cats of the first experimental group at the end of the curation period, the creatinine level decreased by 1.79%, alanine aminotransferase - by 10,40%, the De Rittis coefficient - by 3,93%, glucose - by 10,96% compared to the animals of the second experimental group.

Operative access along the lateral abdominal wall contributed to a more intensive decrease in the serum of animals of the second experimental group of urea concentrations by 1,73%, aspartate aminotransferase - by 2,55%, alkaline

phosphatase - by 1,30%, total bilirubin - by 1,98% compared with operative access along the white line of the abdomen in the first experimental group.

Key words: cats, operational access, ovariectomy, sterilization, blood, red blood cells, platelets.

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Indicators of cochleovestibular disorders in chronic suppurative otitis media"

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Relevance: WHO gives the following definition of chronic otitis media: the presence of persistent discharge from the ear through a perforation in the eardrum for more than 2 weeks], Along with this, patients may note the presence of vestibular symptoms - dizziness and balance disorder. Chronic suppurative otitis media, according to statistics, is one of the most common diseases in otorhinolaryngology and averages 5.8–20.7% of all ENT pathologies. According to domestic authors, the incidence of chronic suppurative otitis media in the Republic of Uzbekistan is up to 6.5%. In 31 cases per 10,000 population, the disease is accompanied by hearing loss with peripheral cochleovestibular disorder. In the world, 28,000 people die every year from complications of chronic suppurative otitis media (mainly from intracranial complications) Vestibular disorders in patients with chronic suppurative otitis media in 37% (dizziness, nausea, gait disturbance) significantly reduce the patient's quality of life.

Purpose of the study: to identify and determine the degree of cochleovestibular disorders in chronic suppurative otitis media

Materials and methods of the study: 95 patients with chronic suppurative otitis media of various forms and duration of the disease were examined at the RSSPMC Pediatrics in the Department of Congenital and Acquired Pathologies of the ENT Organs. Of the 52 patients, there were -45 (52.6%) girls, boys -50 (47.4%). When collecting complaints from patients in dynamics, the following results were obtained: Dizziness 33.7%, tinnitus 41%, nausea 53.8%, discharge from the ear 48.4%, hearing loss 100% a complex of audiological tests, MSCT of the temporal bones. Audiological examination revealed mixed hearing loss in 28 patients, conductive hearing loss in 24 patients. During the examination (VNG) was carried out on the basis of "Intercostals" VNG 405 rotary chair Rotate Chair, Frenzel glasses. The presence of spontaneous nystagmus during VNG examination was

detected in 4 (8%) patients. This group of patients had chronic suppurative otitis media in the form of epitympana. Rotational (Rotation test) revealed positional nystagmus of tone disturbance in 17% of cases, of which 8% did not show vestibular complaints. Air colorization revealed signs of hypofunction of the peripheral vestibular analyzer in 38% of cases. The head shaking test revealed an increase in pathological horizontal nystagmus, taking into account the side of the lesion in 22% of cases. In one patient with chronic suppurative otitis media, concomitant BPPV of the right PPK was detected according to VNG (history of a year ago, RO on the right. Violation of the saccade test, optokinetic nystagmus, smooth tracking within the norm.

CONCLUSIONS

- All patients with chronic suppurative otitis media, regardless of the duration and stage of the inflammatory process, should undergo a comprehensive stylometric diagnosis in order to determine the vestibular status, the degree of involvement of the structures of the inner ear, prognosis, choice of tactics and prevention of complications;
- Complex vitalometry using the high-tech VNG method allows you to reliably differentiate the peripheral and central genesis of dizziness

Fatty hepatitis: effectiveness of various options of pharmaco-dietary therapy

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Material and methods. In order to carry out the research, 149 patients with CKD who underwent inpatient and later outpatient treatment in the therapy and rehabilitation department of the Central Military Hospital under the State Security Service in 2019-2021 were examined.

A total of 149 patients, including 60 (40.3) administrative staff, 43 (28.8) emergency staff, 26 (17.44) emergency security staff, 16 (16) emergency technical staff (10.73%), 4 (2.68%) of the operational-combat team were selected for this study. Their average age was 38.2 ± 6.6 years.

Results. In subgroup B, after 12 months of treatment, GGTP (by $39.6 \pm 5.6\%$, $r < 0.0001$), cholesterol ($16.3 \pm 3.4\%$, $r < 0.001$), ALT ($37.1 \pm$ by 3.2% , $r < 0.001$) significantly decreased and basal glycemia ($16.9 \pm 2.5\%$, $r < 0.01$) compared to baseline values. Comparative analysis with subgroup D revealed significant differences in these parameters ($r < 0.01$, $r < 0.01$, $r < 0.001$ and $r < 0.001$).

After 12 months of therapy in subgroup C patients, alkaline phosphatase ($20.5 \pm 4.4\%$, $p < 0.01$), cholesterol ($15.6 \pm 3.5\%$, $p < 0.01$) at baseline a significant decrease was observed compared to the level. triglycerides ($80.8 \pm 25.0\%$, $p < 0.0001$) and basal glycemia ($12.1 \pm 1.7\%$, $p < 0.001$). These indicators in subgroup C were significantly lower than subgroup D ($p < 0.001$). Alkaline phosphatase and basal glycemia in subgroup C were also significantly lower than subgroup A.

After 12 months of therapy, the analysis of changes in the parameters of the hormonal profile in patients of subgroup A showed a significant decrease in insulin levels compared to the initial data ($43.4 \pm 12.3\%$, $r < 0.001$). A significant decrease in insulin levels ($r < 0.0001$) was found in subgroup A compared to subgroup D.

After 12 months of therapy, insulin levels ($64.1 \pm 19.9\%$, $p < 0.001$) were significantly reduced in patients of subgroup B compared to baseline; comparing the obtained results with subgroup A, no significant differences were found ($p > 0.05$). Comparing the results

of subgroups B and D, a significant decrease in insulin levels ($p < 0.0001$) was found in subgroup B.

Subgroup C patients had a significant decrease in insulin ($103.6 \pm 27.3\%$, $r < 0.0001$) compared to baseline after 12 months of therapy. peptide (by $53.6 \pm 3.7\%$, $r < 0.0001$), while significant dynamics were observed in subgroup C patients compared to subgroup A.

During liver elastography, a decrease in the severity of fibrosis was noted during the treatment of patients with subgroups A, B and C, that is, the number of military patients with fibrosis at stages F0 and F1 increased significantly. Decrease in the number of patients with F3 and F4 fibrosis stages; the detected changes had significant differences with subgroup D ($r < 0.05$, $r < 0.01$, $r < 0.05$ and $r < 0.05$ after 12 months of therapy).

Conclusion. When UDXK and atorvastatin were used in combination with a personalized diet, including control of protein, fat and carbohydrates, in patients with NAFLD, a significant decrease in the main parameters specific to the disease was observed compared to patients of the control group.

The significance of systemic manifestations in shaping the clinical course of the disease in patients with rheumatoid arthritis and autoimmune thyroiditis

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The purpose of the study - to study the role of systemic forms of rheumatoid arthritis (RA) in the course of autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) in the formation of the clinical course of the disease.

Research materials and methods. During the implementation of the study, 189 patients with RA were examined in the rheumatology department of Bukhara regional multidisciplinary medical center (BRMMC) during 2018 and 2020. Based on the results of the questionnaire used in the diagnosis of thyroid pathology, clinical, instrumental and laboratory analyzes of thyroid gland pathology were conducted in all patients treated inpatient, and 82 RA patients (42 RA and 40 RA+AIT) patients and 20 healthy control groups were prospectively selected. Clinical, X-ray, laboratory and immunological examination methods of patients were used for diagnosis. Patients enrolled in a single-stage and prospective comparative study were evaluated on standard physical parameters.

In order to study the degree of damage and risk factors of the thyroid gland in patients with rheumatoid arthritis during the scientific research, all patients were divided into groups with thyroid pathology and those without thyroid pathology, according to the duration of the disease, activity and age of the patients, and the indicators of damage were compared.

Results. In RA with AIT, rheumatoid nodules are 9 (29,4%), generalized amyotrophy 10 (25,7%), neuropathy is the most common and 18,5% of patients with systemic form of RA. Within the group of autoimmune thyroiditis, the systemic form of RA is manifested hypothyroidism 23 (57,5%) the most, and the frequency of meeting is legitimately observed in the aforementioned pathologies.

Summary. Thus, it can be concluded that the systemic forms of RA in combination with AIT are of great importance in shaping the clinical course of the

disease, becoming a serious problem for clinicians and mainly determining its severity and prognosis.

The results obtained during the study and the literature data show that a complete analysis of the nature of the manifestation of systemic symptoms of RA and AIT, the separation of "serious" extra-articular manifestations (with the highest rating for assessing the severity of RA) and the timely identification of aggressive and rapidly developing pathology, provides an opportunity to facilitate a rational approach to the selection of early and active therapy.

Assessment of clinical characteristics of acute sinusitis, accompanied with allergic rhinitis in children

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Relevance. Allergic rhinitis (AR) - chronic disease of the nasal cavity, the pathogenesis of which is 1 E - mediated inflammation of the nasal mucosa. AR is determined in 10-20% of the child population [4]. In children, AR leads to various restrictions in activity, a decrease in the quality of the physical, psychological and social aspects of life [2].

Thus, it is relevant to look for alternative methods for studying SNPs that meet the requirements of otolaryngologists and can be used not only for diagnosis, but also in the process of dynamic monitoring of the disease. [1,3].

The method should be informative and safe. These methods include two-dimensional ultrasound (ultrasound), but the method of its use in the diagnosis of sinusitis in children has not been developed.

Purpose of the study. The aim of the study is to study clinical and experimental features of acute sinusitis in children with AR in order to increase the effectiveness of the treatment of this pathology.

Materials and research methods. To solve the set before us task, we examined a total of 75 children admitted to the department of otorhinolaryngology with acute sinusitis. In order to improve the effectiveness of their treatment, we studied the clinical and experimental features of acute sinusitis in children with allergic rhinitis.

Research results. Time of mucociliary transport and motor activity of the ciliated epithelium of the nasal mucosa in healthy children has no age and sex differences. Normally, the time of the saccharin test in children is 7.54 ± 0.34 minutes. The frequency of cilia beating in different anatomical zones of the nasal cavity in childhood is different and equal to 3.19 ± 1.71 Hz on the inferior turbinate, and 6.95 ± 2.36 Hz on the middle turbinate ($p < 0.001$).

In acute purulent sinusitis in children, a significant lengthening of the time of the saccharin test to 10.84 ± 0.49 minutes is observed. and a decrease in the motor

activity of the ciliary apparatus of the nasal mucosa to 0.34 ± 0.26 Hz on the inferior turbinate and 3.42 ± 2.17 Hz on the middle turbinate.

As the child grows, there is a change in the main indicators of nasal breathing in the form of an increase in the total volumetric flow and a decrease in nasal resistance, while there are no significant gender differences. The most significant dynamics of the respiratory function of the nasal cavity in children falls on the period of primary school (7-10 years) and adolescence (15-17 years).

The nasal cycle is present in 95% of healthy children and in 66.7% of children with sinusitis. In childhood, the non-classical nasal cycle dominates. In inflammatory processes in the paranasal sinuses, the frequency of fluctuations is shorter than normal, but their species identity is preserved, which allows us to consider the nasal cycle as a persistent physiological phenomenon that reflects the reactivity of the nasal mucosa.

The negative pressure created in the nasal cavity during the YAMIK procedure does not significantly affect the functional state of the nasal cavity. After applying the sinus catheter, there is no persistent inhibition of mucociliary transport and motor activity of the ciliated epithelium, which can serve as evidence of the safety of the YAMIK method.

Conclusion. To evaluate the results of treatment of children with sinusitis, it is recommended use two-dimensional ultrasonography as a safe and informative research method. The criterion for sanitation of the paranasal sinuses on ultrasound scans is the absence of any echogenic signals in the projection of the sinuses.

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PEDAGOGY

Importance and benefits of e-learning.

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Annotation:

Teaching strategies, as well as methods, have always been paying great attention in pedagogy. It was shaped and evolved over centuries based on the path of development and political views of the education system.

The effectiveness of the learning process, the proper implementation of the intended goal and the desired outcome, requires significant strategic planning, which should equally involve both the teacher and the administration of the educational institutions.

For today, there are several teaching strategies in modern pedagogy to build a person equipped with democratic values:

Keywords: student, e-learning, process, knowledge

- “Cognitive strategy-means learning, processing, analyzing, critically evaluating and applying pupils to different situations;
- Metacognitive (self-thinking) strategy-means actively engaging the learner in planning, managing, monitoring and evaluating their own learning process;
- Emotional – motivational strategies-meant to create a positive attitude towards the subject studied;
- “Resource – based strategies – means effective use of multimedia, network-based learning tools in the learning process”. (Basil adze and others. 2016).

All four teaching strategies focus on making the pupil/student aware and active involvement in the learning process; however, in the trail of unprecedented development of information and resources, multimedia, networking miracle The effective use of VLO tools to create an interactive learning environment has an important place.

“Distance learning can be considered as 1728, when the boston gazette first appeared, a teacher was looking for applicants to send materials once a week”. this method was actively used in the 19th century after the refinement of the postal system. Since then and into the late twentieth century, this system has evolved and evolved, but only after the spread of computers and the internet”.

The spread of the Internet and the advancement of computer technologies have led to “on-line learning” as a new form of distance learning.

Today a person can take a course in any other country in the world. Years ago, it was incredible to get an education in the world's famous universities without leaving the country. One of the advantages of this method is that a student has the opportunity to study in several universities at the same time.

Studying online is cheaper than studying on-site and a graduate gets the exact same diploma he would get on-site. Distance learning is recognized as a serious alternative to higher education in the developed world and a really comfortable and convenient way to study for those seeking different specialties. Accordingly, more and more people choose to continue studying in a "virtual university".

It is widely known that with the implementation of distance learning, a large number of those who want to get education without interruption from their basic work, at any time and regardless of their location of residence. In addition, it is a realistic and flexible way of accelerated higher education with significant savings of time and financial resources.

Student numbers at leading European and American universities do not exceed virtual students. This trend is characterized by growing and ascending dynamics for other universities as well.

Remarkably, distance learning creates good learning conditions for students with disabilities and those in penitentiary institutions. Adopting new technologies in teaching is a top state priority in many countries around the world.

This teaching format and its methodology is latest and innovative and brings many benefits to delivering interactive learning and Offers opportunity to both student and

teacher. Adopting and implementing Internet technologies in all spheres is a legal process for learning and establishing a new way of life. This teaching format provides the student with so much in-depth and comprehensive information, enriched with effective insights that are not available in traditional teaching methods. She is expanding her teaching capabilities dramatically.

E-learning is a new method of acquiring knowledge using electronic technologies such as telecommunication, television, multimedia, satellite channel data transmission and computer networks. The advantage of e-learning is that the student chooses the place and time to study and email for communication. Student see syllabus as per his/her specialty (Review consultations, enrollment, examinations etc.) S T H I N G I N G) and the curriculum (according to the semester subjects, thesis draft). Then the student works independently and according to a particular subject, goes to review consultations, or takes useful advice from a tutor according to the predetermined schedule. The student will send the control thesis, bachelor thesis to the email. It is noteworthy that the first steps in this regard have already been taken by the Ministry of Punishment, Probation and Legal Aid, which signed a special memorandum with several high schools. This learning method is already available to prisoners, some of whom we know successfully passed Unified National Exams, followed by learning electronically at the university.

What is distance learning in general?

"Distance learning means long-distance learning when two subjects - the student and the lecturer are separated from each other, in both time and space" (Kupatadze, 2009).

Such a definition may be confusing; but it is true because much of learning at this time is taking place using modern information technology and state-of-the-art telecommunication systems. It is now a form of teaching designed specifically for a student or group of students who are not physically present in a traditional auditorium or cabinet, but this does not imply communication between students, or

student and lecturer It's reduced in between. Well-organized eLearning diversifies teaching and learning styles without excluding the role of active communication.

It is “the process that makes learning accessible when the source of information and the recipient are separated by time, space or both” (Kupatadze, 2009).

Therefore, it is an organized system which has the capacity to perfectly provide education to student via computer and internet like it is a daily going and lecture system in University The tour will be based on attendance. "Such a system should be able to control the learning process perfectly, ensure the connection between the student and the lecturer" (GESJ: Education Science and Psychology 2012 | No.1(20) International Scientific Conference: "Education in the Era of GL oblalization - XXI Century Challenges". Materials ISSN 1512-18016). The definition of e-learning itself (full, hybrid and face-to-face) and the quality of its application in the learning process is designed and defined accordingly.

In general, during e-learning, the learning material is provided to the student via the global network of the Internet using modern software and technology without geographical i.e., spatial factors cannot affect the learning in the making of s. As for catching up with the pupil and the teacher on time, it is not necessary, because the student will search the learning material posted on the Internet at any time and, if necessary, the teacher will record it there (on the Internet) Reading and required consultation questions, prepares proper answer packets, post them (online) for the student to use within their preferred time period, and depending It won't be on the teacher. Unlike traditional teaching methods, the main feature of e-learning is that the pupil/student acquires the desired knowledge independently. This is done using advanced information resources that are presented by modern information technology and available to a broad audience. In this case, we will have "computer knowledge bases, trainers of different scale and purposes, video and audio recordings, multimedia, electronic manuals, consulting and control systems" (Catharize, it's a floor plan. 2004). “The Internet (unlike TV learning) has significantly reduced both the time and financial costs of dissemination of

information as it has created itself to integrate its own database of information structures, the information it represents.” Educational programs' basic nursery" (Catharize, Sartain, 2004).

As we noted earlier, teaching effectiveness depends greatly on how the learning material is organized, the level of management methodology and the means of its implementation to ensure that the internet connection between the student and the lecturer is intact Tereso, continuous and at the same time, maintain maximum individuality.

In addition, the effectiveness of e-learning also depends on the level of learning-didactic principles are implemented, whether the psychological characteristics of a student's perception of information are taken into account, or not Bulli software and networking resources.

Resume of the past

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E-learning is not a new method of acquiring knowledge, the advantage of e-learning is that the student chooses the place and time for learning, and e-mail for communication. This learning method is already available to incarcerated students, with some of whom we know successfully passed the Unified National Exams, then also studying electronically at the university.

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STATE AND LAW

The Feminist Discourse in the works of Sylvia Plath

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Iakob Gogebashvili Telavi State University, 2022

Assoc.Professor **Nino Gogiashvili**

My report will be about feminism and the work of Sylvia Plath. Why Plath and why I will conduct a discourse around her? - Plath is one of the greatest figures of American literature, who further strengthened the idea of feminism and showed us the vicious sides of the dominant patriarchy. I will start with what feminism is and what idea it serves.

Feminism is a social and political movement whose goal is to recognize and equalize the rights of women with men in all spheres of life, be it social, political, cultural or otherwise. Feminist includes three theories: sociological, political and philological.

Key words:

Feminist, poetry, Sylvia Plath, American, literature,

The first form of feminism originated in China, but America, with its declaration, adopted in 1776, fleshed out the idea of protecting women's rights. There are three waves of the feminist movement: the goal of the first was the right to vote in elections, the second served to liberate women from social and sexual character. This wave was greatly strengthened by Simone de Beauvoir's work "The Second Sex" and his phrase "They are not born women, they become women" became one of the slogans of feminism. The third wave is the continuation of the second one and involves the fight against gender oppression. The main goal of feminism is to Women should have freedom of education, work, reproductive and sexual freedom, and freedom of choice in general. When talking about feminism, we cannot fail to mention Mary Watercraft, who challenged the prevailing views on women's rights and women as individuals in general. In her work "Protection of Women's Rights", which he published in 1792, she argued how rights less and miserable a woman's life is. With his work, she made a significant contribution to women's rights and education. Feminism is still relevant today, because we often face differences

between the sexes in various social spheres, the world has not yet been freed from patriarchy, and women's rights are often violated, so discussing this issue is a relevant topic at all times. When talking about feminism, we cannot fail to mention Mary Watercraft, who challenged the prevailing views on women's rights and women as individuals in general. In his work "Protection of Women's Rights", which he published in 1792, she argued how rights less and miserable a woman's life is. With she works, made a significant contribution to women's rights and education. Feminism is still relevant today, because we often face differences between the sexes in various social spheres, the world has not yet been freed from patriarchy, and women's rights are often violated, so discussing this issue is a relevant topic at all times. When talking about feminism, we cannot fail to mention Mary Watercraft, who challenged the prevailing views on women's rights and women as individuals in general. In his work "Protection of Women's Rights", which he published in 1792, he argued how rights less and miserable a woman's life is. With his work, she made a significant contribution to women's rights and education. Feminism is still relevant today, because we often face differences between the sexes in various social spheres, the world has not yet been freed from patriarchy, and women's rights are often violated, so discussing this issue is a relevant topic at all times. Argumentally, she has justified how rights less and miserable a woman's life is. With his work, she made a significant contribution to women's rights and education. Feminism is still relevant today, because we often face differences between the sexes in various social spheres, the world has not yet been freed from patriarchy, and women's rights are often violated, so discussing this issue is a relevant topic at all times. Argument ally, she has justified how rights less and miserable a woman's life is. With her work, she made a significant contribution to women's rights and education. Feminism is still relevant today, because we often face differences between the sexes in various social spheres, the world has not yet been freed from patriarchy, and women's rights are often violated, so discussing this issue is a relevant topic at all times.

The main character of my report, Sylvia Plath, also suffered from the double standards that a woman should be a good housewife, a caring, devoted wife and a loving mother who should give up her ambitions. Writing takes time, as well as thinking and immersing yourself in your body, exploring your soul, but you find that you have time for nothing but family. Sylvia Plath was a little girl with great talent and a loving heart who was abandoned and left alone with two young children. A small girl with a delicate soul, she suffered from severe depression because she couldn't...she couldn't do it like a man. According to him, everything was easy for men, they would love you, give you the world and one day they would disappear from your life without any responsibility. A heartbroken and hopeless Plath wrote. She wrote about everything that bothered him, told us how it hurt and what he thought about society. from whom she asked for help. What a trash to annihilate each decade. What a million filaments. The peanut-crunching crowd Shoves in to see Them unwrap me hand and foot—— The big strip tease. Gentlemen, ladies These are my hands My knees. I may be skin and bones, nevertheless, I am the same, identical woman. The first time it happened I was ten. It was an accident. The second time I meant to last it out and not come back at all. I rocked shut as a seashell. They had to call and call and pick the worms off me like sticky pearls. Dying is an art, like everything else. I do it exceptionally well." (Nevertheless, I am the same, identical woman. The first time it happened I was ten. It was an accident. The second time I meant to last it out and not come back at all. I rocked shut as a seashell. They had to call and call and pick the worms off me like sticky pearls. Dying is an art, like everything else. I do it exceptionally well." (Nevertheless, I am the same, identical woman. The first time it happened I was ten. It was an accident. The second time I meant to last it out and not come back at all. I rocked shut as a seashell. They had to call and call and pick the worms off me like sticky pearls. Dying is an art, like everything else. I do it exceptionally well." (What It's crazy—destroy decades. hair's thin strand—millions. crowd Yes—land Nuts Aknatunes, the neck continues, that to see the hand and leg how They will explain to me—huge, bare, to the squeamish.

Gentlemen, Ladies, Here, this is my Arms, my Knees. bone, skin I am, But anyway—the same woman. of ten I was—all at first. unhappy case was. for the second time-I wanted no return. I lived, locked like a sink, and I They called me, as sticky pearls, worms They chased me for a long time. death is art, Well, as other everything. however, I it on everything better it works for me.) -. Born in Boston in 1932, that girl could not even imagine that she would speak to the world with her creativity and biography. Constant psychological traumas followed her from childhood, and creativity reflects her life like a mirror. It was Sylvia who laid the foundation for the "confessional" style of writing, she was the first woman who said in her work that she was mentally ill. Female authors always masked their emotions and after reading the work, we knew nothing about them. Sylvia Plath's only prose work "Zarkhuf" is often compared to Salinger's "A Game in the Rye", although if Salinger's writing style is convention, in Plath's case it is her life.

The main purpose of the report is to present how Plath turned her pain into creativity and how she earned her place in feminist literature.

It was impossible for her to be versatile as a woman-poet and as a mother. On one side was her career and aspiration towards poetry, on the other she had to be a housewife. "I saw my life branching out before me like the green fig tree in the story. From the tip of every branch, like a fat purple fig, a wonderful future beckoned and winked. One fig was a husband and a happy home and children, and another fig was a famous poet and another fig was a brilliant professor, and another fig was Ee Gee, the amazing editor, and another fig was Europe and Africa and South America, and another fig was Constantin and Socrates and Attila and a pack of other lovers with queer names and offbeat professions, and another fig was an Olympic lady crew champion, and beyond and above these figs were many more figs I couldn't quite make out. I saw myself sitting in the crotch of this fig tree, starving to death, just because I couldn't make up my mind which of the figs I would choose. I wanted each and every one of them, but choosing one meant losing all the rest, and, as I sat there, unable to decide, the figs began to wrinkle and go black, and, one by one, they

popped to the ground at my feet. "my life I saw mine in front branched, as fig a tree. Every from the side wonderful future-ripe, Violet fig like eye He played me and called me. one Fig husband was and happy house and children; second Fig was brilliant Professor; and other Fig was Excellent editor; and other Fig was-Europe and Africa and South America...this figs except and this figs beyond was again lots of Fig, which now in the eye no I understood. my myself I could see and I was sitting this by the tree and from hunger soul I was moving, because that no I knew it which one Fig I decided of them one by one all I wanted, But one S choose of others loss meant than so I was sitting and Can't decide for me A Figs They were withering and They were getting black and at the feet They were falling.") writes Plath in her novel and accurately describes the cause of her depression, not with his creative hand, but his soul purified poetry.

His poem "mirror" is an internal monologue, which is confirmed by the structure of the poem along with the content: it contains elliptical sentences that take us on a journey through the past and the present together with the author. Lexis monologue expresses the emotions and desires that occupy his mind. "Memories make life beautiful, but forgetting makes life unbearable" - this phrase of Balzac was an admonition for her to forget her desires and dreams, to be like all the women around her, although Sylvia could not be like everyone else.

With her creativity, she challenges the society, where the idea is established that a woman has no right to approach her dream, while a man has all the ways open. This opinion was supported by the success in poetry of her ex-husband Ted Hughes, who was not concerned about the children or Plath's mental state. He loved Ted until the last moment of his life. When you read her poems, you think that someone thought the same way as you, wrote for you and cried with you, you realize that you are gradually losing your mind, you discover that Sylvia Plath is happening to you too or you already had it and you didn't know it. said, But I grow old and I forget your name. (I think I made you up inside my head.) I should have loved a thunderbird

instead; At least when spring comes, they roar back again. I shut my eyes and all the world drops dead. (I think I made you up inside my head.)

In a feminist perspective, Plath shows us what can happen to a person when you don't allow them to use their potential. If we borrow from Mary Wollstonecraft, "the mind is divine in man and its use is the purpose of a woman and a man" (Tskhadadze 2017, 236)

It is this fact and the traumas of life that cause a severe depression in Plath, he asks for help from the society, which at this time is busy eating nuts, "The peanut-crunching crowd"

All her poems echo hopelessness, heartbreak and disappointment, and he sees the only way out in quick and painless death. Her last leis is a kind of prophecy of the end, the woman has been perfected, her corpse is adorned with a smile of victory, the illusion of a Greek statue disappears in the folds of the toga, and her bare feet seem to say: we have come this far and it is all over" (margin)

In 1963, Plath committed suicide. She died very beautiful and grew up new, because if there was no love, if there was no life that was offered, she needed someone to love her, whose side she could stand on, and in whose eyes, she could read unconditional love. He killed himself he is now lying in the grave, probably his bones are no longer left and his soul is bleeding like blood from our pains.

used literature:

literature: <https://mypoeticside.com/poets/sylvia-plath-poems><https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0F1xgQKfOhg>

The importance of the world trade organization in the modern world

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Annotation: This article examines the importance of the WTO in the modern world, the goals and objectives of the organization, analyzes international legal documents, a brief history of the organization's creation. The final part of the article presents conclusions on the creation and significance of the organization.

Keywords: World Trade Organization, General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade, trade policy, Marrakesh Agreement, creation, international legal documents, organization.

The World Trade Organization (WTO) is an international organization established on January 1, 1995 with the aim of liberalizing international trade and regulating trade and political relations of member States. The WTO was formed on the basis of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) of 1947 and actually performed the functions of an international organization, but was not legally such.

The important objectives of the WTO are: to raise the standard of living of people in the member countries, to ensure full employment and a broad increase in effective demand, to expand production and trade in goods, to increase trade in services, to ensure optimal use of world resources, to ensure environmental protection, and so on.

The WTO is a mechanism for the implementation, administration and implementation of the provisions of multilateral trade agreements. The WTO in its activities applies the GATT practice, decisions, procedures and decision-making methods established in the GATT.

The creation of the WTO entailed serious changes in the general system of rights and obligations arising in the conduct of trade. Thus, the Contracting Parties to the 1947 GATT, becoming WTO member States, must, without any exceptions or reservations, accept the MTS (Multilateral Trade Agreements) included in Annexes 1, 2, 3 of the WTO Agreement, as well as submit their lists of concessions

in respect of goods and specific sectoral and subsectoral concessions on access issues the market and the national regime in trade in services.

This has led to a significant expansion in the scope of obligations of all GATT Contracting Parties, but developing countries, in particular, will face a sharp increase in the level of their obligations, especially in the agricultural sector, as well as new obligations in the field of trade in services and in the field of intellectual property rights. Thus, very strict conditions for joining the WTO pose a serious problem for them. The WTO significantly limits the flexibility of trade policy.

The process of joining the Organization is also seriously complicated for those developing countries and countries with economies in transition that are currently negotiating the terms of their accession to the GATT, as they have to adapt to the new agreements concluded during the Uruguay Round.

From the point of view of Velyaminov G.M., at present the WTO is the only real center for the development of legal conditions, principles and norms of international trade on a global scale.

The study of the international legal literature on WTO law has shown that there is no single approach to the definition of WTO law in the scientific literature. From the point of view of A.N. Mitin, "The World Trade Organization is at the same time a set of legal documents, a kind of multilateral trade agreement defining the rights and obligations of governments in the field of international trade in goods and services" [1].

We believe that such fundamentally different legal categories as "organization" and "contract" should not be confused. A similar confusion occurs with respect to the GATT, which by its legal nature is an agreement (contract), but is considered by some researchers as an international organization.

It seems that the legal constructions "organization" and "contract", developed by legal science and practice over centuries of progressive development, have their own legal regime, their own goals and objectives, and features of functioning within the framework of legal matter.

According to V.M. Shumilov, "WTO law includes the norms of the Agreement on the Establishment of the WTO, all other agreements and acts that make up the WTO package, acts adopted by WTO bodies. These norms and acts ensure global trade law and order, represent a unique phenomenon - a phenomenon of global and historical significance, characterized by a number of features and features»[2].

The main source of WTO law is the Marrakesh WTO Agreement and its annexes. The Marrakesh WTO Agreement consists of only 16 articles: They briefly describe the objectives, functions, bodies of the WTO, membership and decision-making process in the WTO. However, 18 international treaties that form an integral part of the Marrakesh WTO Agreement are attached to this short text.

The Marrakesh WTO Agreement does not define what legal consequences WTO law generates in the internal legal order of WTO members. Each WTO member is left to decide independently whether acts of its domestic law can be appealed in its national courts because of non-compliance with WTO law. Most WTO members do not allow direct reference to WTO law in their national courts. In other words, WTO law has no direct application in the national legal order of the majority of WTO members.

The purpose of these agreements is to ensure that trade takes place as smoothly, predictably and freely as possible.

In our opinion, WTO law is a system of norms arranged according to a certain internal structure and hierarchy of these norms, which comprehensively regulates public relations in the trade sphere (establishing the global trade law and order), as well as the accompanying organizational relations between the WTO member countries. The WTO legal system is a complex, complex international legal system phenomenon.

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TECHNOLOGY

Construction of Surveillance Model based on ARDUINO UNO

Using the Digital Shlagbaum Prototype as an Example

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Abstract

The article covers the purpose and basic operating principles of the most common Arduino UNO model. The modelling and construction of a research project entitled 'Digital Shlagbaum' based on the use of the characteristics of an ultrasonic sensor unit is used to illustrate the technical aspects of using Arduino UNO (Ultrasonic-HC-SR04).

In this study, the development of the project model and its practical use in both a virtual and real-world setting are demonstrated and closely analyzed. Particularly used were the Arduino Software IDE (Integrated Development Environment) local programming editor, the Arduino UNO working board, and the virtual online platform tinkercad.com.

keywords: Arduino UNO; Arduino IDE; STEM; tinkercad.com; Ultrasonic sensor HC-SR04.

Introduction

In today's educational space, working on STEM-type (STEM - Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) research projects, which involve the

integration of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics into problem-solving processes are given major emphasis. Arduino can be considered one of the unique tools for implementing STEM-type research projects. (Mosashvili I., Oniani S. 2016); (Tabatadze Z., Todua T. 2019); (Geddes, Mark. 2016). (Nancy N. Heilbronner 2014) [Global Education Innovation Initiative](#)

Currently, there are many organizations involved in STEM education including [Global Education Innovation Initiative](#); [Bootstrap](#); [E2 Young Engineers \(ESYE\)](#); [Earth Force](#); [Engineering for Kids](#); [PAUTA: Programa Adopte Un Talento](#); [Practical Education Network\(PEN\)](#); [VentuteLab](#)

Thus, the research goal of the given work this time was to study the tinkercad.com online resource, ARDUINO IDE programming editor, and technological aspects of ARDUINO UNO while building a model of the STEM research project 'Digital Shlagbaum', both in virtual and real contexts.

The research project was carried out in an informal setting under the guidance of Professor Mariam Zakariashvili of the Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences of Telavi I. Gogebashvili State University.

Contents

Organizational, technological and programming structure of the STEM research project 'Digital Shlagbaum'.

Project name: 'Digital Shlagbaum'

The goal of the project: Building or automating control of the 'digital Shlagbaum' model using an ultrasonic sensor.

The project model's algorithm is described as follows: When a vehicle is within a specified distance, an ultrasonic sensor detects it and opens the Shlagbaum. A voice message then activates, the green light turns on, and a text recording confirming the vehicle's passage is displayed on the monitor. In the event that this doesn't occur, the Shlagbaum is closed, the audio message is over, the red light is on, and the monitor recording is set to no-move. The prototype of the Shlagbaum in the project's design is the rotating arrow mounted on a servo motor.

Components required to build a project model:

Arduino UNO; Breadboard; Arduino USB 2.0.Cable Ultrasonic Distance Sensor, Micro Servo; Piezo; LCD 16x2; Potentiometer; Resistor; Led green; Led red; Led RGB; Jumper wires; Tape measure manual.

Applications and online resources:

- <https://www.tinkercad.com/> Using Tinkercad, it's possible to create virtual projects, run various commands through electronic circuits, develop and debug program codes, as well as manage or simulate the system automatically in line with the code. The platform is open source. Registration/authorization is easy using a Gmail account.
- [Arduino Software IDE](https://www.arduino.cc/en/software) is also an open-source software editor that enables to design of the code required for a product to function and specifies what the product will do using the Arduino IDE and Arduino UNO programming language. It's available to download and install the Arduino IDE installation package for Windows for free from the website address <https://www.arduino.cc/en/software>.

The physical essence of the ultrasonic sensor

Ultrasonic sensor HC-SR04 can measure distance. It emits ultrasound at a frequency of 40,000 Hz (40 kHz), which propagates through the air and, if an object/obstacle appears in its path, returns to the module. Given the travel time and the speed of sound, the distance can be calculated. For example, if an object is 70 cm away from the sensor and the speed of sound is 340 m/s or 0.034 cm/ms, it will take the sound wave ≈ 2058.82 ms to cover 70 cm. But what you get from the Echo pin will be a double number because the sound wave has to move back and forth. Therefore, to get the distance in cm, it is necessary to multiply the travel time obtained from the echo pin by 0.034 m/s and divide it by 2. The sound speed $V=340$ m/s (m/s); If convert $V=0.034$ cm/microsecond (cm/ μ s) $\text{time}=\text{distance}/\text{velocity}$; $t=S/V=(70 \text{ cm}/(0.034 \text{ cm/microsecond}) \approx 2058.82 \text{ m/s}$ (double time $t=2058.82*2=4117.64 \text{ ms}$) $S=(t*0.034)/2$ ($S= (4117*0.034)/2 = 139,999/2 \approx 69.999 \approx 70 \text{ cm}$ (See Fig. N1 -

Ultrasonic sound model; N2 - Sound propagation) See additional instructions via the link [ultrasound sensor](#).

The configuration pins of the ultrasonic HC-SR04 are the following: VCC(1), TRIG(2), ECHO(3) and GND(4). VCC supply voltage is +5V; The negative of GND and TRIG and ECHO pins can be connected to any digital I/O on the Arduino board.

Fig. N1 Ultrasonic sound model

Fig. N2 Sound propagation

Project Implementation Stages

Initial stage - The first step consists of creating the electronic circuit and programming for the virtual model in the tinkercad.com environment. (For a virtual circuit model, see Fig. N3) Visit the following URL to get the virtual circuit and project source code:

<https://www.tinkercad.com/things/ev4PnnoFtQw>

The second stage - Constructing the real electronic circuit under the virtual circuit (see Fig. N4 - real circuit model).

The third stage- The integration of the circuit with the computer code is the next step. Participants in the project copy the code from Tinkercad and paste it into the Arduino Software IDE editor. They next attach an actual Arduino UNO platform-built circuit to the Arduino IDE, debug it, and upload program code to the Arduino UNO. (Arduino IDE + Tinkercad + Arduino UNO) (see Fig. N5 - practical implementation of the project). See the Arduino IDE code file at the following link for comprehensive **instructions**:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/19ReyArxO5750T0m0Qnnucm92nt6D_VsB?usp=sharing

Fig. 3 Virtual circuit model Fig. N4 Real circuit model fig. N5 Practical implementation of the project

The fourth stage is the verification of the results of the completed project. The object is placed in front of the ultrasonic sensor at different distances and the pre-planned and obtained results are checked on the Arduino IDE serial monitor and LCD device. The result will also be verified with a normal centimetre tape, and the necessary deductions are made. Visit the following link to view the functionality of the actual project model:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/19ReyArxO5750T0m0Qnnum92nt6D_VsB?usp=sharing

Conclusion

The article details the process of building an Arduino-based surveillance model in virtual and real settings as part of the 'Digital Shlagbaum' research project. The Shlagbaum prototype operated well in a real context providing proof that the project was implemented successfully.

The presented project model can be used in modeling and automatic control of 'smart devices' focused on ultrasonic sensors.

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Advantages of Natural Juices compared to Non-alcoholic Drinks

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The human body is a self-renewing system and the basis of its animal activity is nutrition. Nutrition is a vital process that ensures the growth and development of the body, work capacity, health, and longevity. Nutrition is one of the main conditions for the spiritual and physical development of a person, with food a person receives 70% of the substances necessary for the body. 30% - with water and air.

Natural fruit and vegetable juices have a special place in the human diet; The result of multiple studies is that fruits and vegetables are considered very valuable food products, and the juices obtained from them contain all the edible components of fresh fruits and vegetables (carbohydrates, minerals, water-soluble vitamins, etc.), which, despite the difference in the technologies of their reception, pass perfectly into the juice.

Our aim is to demonstrate the superiority of natural fruit and vegetable juices compared to non-alcoholic soft drinks made using different food additives (colors, preservatives, antioxidants, sweeteners) based on various literature and electronic information we searched for.

Juices are natural liquid products obtained from undamaged and ripe fruits and vegetables. They contain only useful substances necessary for the human body, which are transferred to them from the original raw materials.

Fruit and berry juices have dietary and in some cases medicinal value, they help food absorption and improve metabolism in the body.

Nitrogenous compounds, sugars, polysaccharides, organic acids, tanning and dyeing substances, vitamins, mineral substances and others are significant from the nutrients contained in juices.

Vitamins contained in juices play an important role not only in physiological processes, but also in the animal activity of the whole body. For example, vitamin C or ascorbic acid, the lack of which causes diabetes, also affects the body's

carbohydrate and nitrogen metabolism. It should be noted that vitamin C is not synthesized in the human body and its balance is regulated by food intake.

Vitamin A is also important, which is found in fruits and vegetables in the form of provitamin carotene and turns into vitamin A upon entering the human body. Carotene is mainly contained in pulp juice. Natural fruit juices are also rich in vitamins of group B, which are necessary for the body's vital processes.

There are enough organic acids in natural fruit juices: apple, lemon, wine, there are relatively small amounts of amber, salicylic acids and others. They give fruit juices a pleasant sour taste and have a refreshing effect on the body. There are sufficient amounts of phenolic compounds in natural juices, the presence of which creates a specific taste characteristic of fruit juices together with sugars and organic acids.

In addition, natural fruit juices are rich in mineral substances and microelements, which overall play a major role in maintaining the basicity of the blood. Potassium salts are noteworthy among them. There is a lot of potassium in apple, pear, apricot, grape juice. Relatively small amounts of juices contain phosphorus, calcium, sulfur, manganese.

As a result of recent researches, it was established that untreated juices (with pulp) contain pectin substances with anti-radiation and anti-toxic properties, which have the ability to expel heavy metals, toxins, radioactive elements from the human body as a result of direct connection with them.

There is a large content of pectin's in the pulpy juice of apples, quinces, and black currants

When evaluating fruit and vegetable juices, great importance is attached to their naturalness indicator, for which the technological regime that results in natural fruit and vegetable juices must be strictly followed in order to completely separate and preserve all the nutrients contained in fresh fruits and vegetables, otherwise the juice changes chemical composition and a completely different product is obtained. A positive feature of natural fruit and vegetable juices is that it can be used throughout the year regardless of the season, which is its greatest value as a natural product.

Despite the fact that the production of natural fruit and vegetable juices is developing at a fast pace in the world, the demand of a large part of the population cannot be satisfied, especially for juices intended for children's diet.

Today, in the conditions of scientific and technical progress and economic globalization, the assortment of non-alcoholic soft drinks has been significantly expanded, new non-traditional technological methods of production, storage and sale have been introduced, the amount of chemical substances used in them, called food additives (dyes, sweeteners, preservatives, antioxidants and others) has increased dramatically.) variety and quantity, which created a favorable basis for the production of counterfeit products.

Food additives, which are used to improve non-alcoholic soft drinks production, transportation, production process improvement or refinement, product structure, appearance or organoleptic properties (color, taste, smell), have become a useful tool of fraudsters in the hands of unscrupulous entrepreneurs.

In all developed countries, the content of additives in food products is strictly regulated, violation of the consumption norm of these substances causes the accumulation of toxic chemical substances in the body and negative effects on health.

The issue of food safety has always been active, and the problems related to it have their origin even in ancient times. Many rules or recommendations found in books of a historical or religious nature are a clear attempt to protect people from foodborne illnesses.

Safety, which is one of the most important consumer properties of a food product taken by humans, implies that the product should not cause any harm to human health during consumption, both in the short term (poisoning, infections) and in the long term (carcinogenic, mutagenic effects). It should be emphasized that in this regard, the situation in Georgia is not very favorable, both in relation to domestic and imported food products, it is worth noting the lack of control of non-alcoholic soft drinks.

During the adulteration of food products, there is a falsification of one or more characteristics of the product. Several types of falsification are distinguished: assortment, type, quantity, value, informational, technological, complex. All of them apply to non-alcoholic soft drinks.

Falsification is a mercenary act to falsify the object of purchase and sale, and its purpose is to maximize profit, at the expense of harming the interests of a legitimate entrepreneur.

During the falsification of non-alcoholic soft drinks, the product retains the typical characteristics characteristic of naturalness (appearance, color, consistency), but loses not only important components for nutritional value (high-value carbohydrates, vitamins, etc.), but also often becomes dangerous for human health, falsification is especially dangerous when forgery They use sugar substitutes and artificial colors. As is known, the use of sugar substitutes is recommended mainly for diabetics, and their frequent use for children often leads to carbohydrate metabolism disorders. Aspartame (Sladex) is mainly used for this purpose. In more than 90 countries, especially for diabetics. It is low-calorie, 200 times sweeter than sugar.

It should be noted that aspartame is a dangerous substance accidentally discovered by chemist James Schlattel in 1965. In 1944, 90 different symptoms were documented as a result of aspartame intake, in short, aspartame destroys the brain, CNS, can damage all organs, many doctors concluded that aspartame is a drug, not a compound of nutritional value. Symptoms of aspartame poisoning include: muscle pain, numbness in the limbs, depression, panic attacks, dry tongue, absent-mindedness, and others.

Aspartame consists of 3 chemical compounds: aspartamic acid 40%, phenylallylin 50%, methanol 10%, all three of them are risk factors.

James and Phyllis Balkh's book refers to it as a "chemical poison": large amounts of aspartame cause a complicated form of nervousness that can lead to death.

Cases of aspartame poisoning have been documented in the USA. The reason for the poisoning is that when the soft drink is stored at 30°C, aspartame can break down to form methanol and phenylalanine, both of which are toxic, especially methanol, which affects the CNS.

In addition, artificial colors are used in the production of non-alcoholic soft drinks. Some of them, which are used more often, are characterized by carcinogenic properties. These are: Amaranite, Sudan III, Tartrazine, Azorubin E122, Ponceau 4R (E124) and others. They can cause various types of toxicosis and decrease immunity. According to American experts (Center for science in the public interest, CSPI, etc.), banning the use of synthetic dyes is necessary to prevent risks to children's health. It has been proven that synthetic dyes cause attention deficit syndrome, brain neurosis, epilepsy, headaches. Such children have difficulty in learning, have incorrect speech, inadequate action, which is often accompanied by aggression. The treatment of the disease is rather difficult, because for this, powerful drugs are used, which are potentially dangerous for the adolescent body.

Conservants are added to non-alcoholic drinks in order to increase their shelf life, although this is not indicated either on the labeling or on the accompanying documents.

For beverages, water is the most common means of adulteration. The safety level of the non-alcoholic drink adulterated by this method strongly depends on the quality of the water used. If the microbiological indicators of the used water are unsatisfactory, the drink made from such water is harmful to human health.

Regarding the consumer's attitude towards food additives, we cite the results of a survey conducted by the "Association of Food Experts" (2007), where 91% are convinced that manufacturers hide the presence of additives in products.

The presence of preservatives in the product (63%), 21% "afraid" of emulsifiers, dyes - 12%, stabilizers - 2.5%, sugar substitutes - 1.5% cause distrust among consumers.

The degree of distrust of consumers towards food additives of different groups, it is necessary to inform the population more about the negative consequences of using food additives, most of which are obtained by genetic engineering, restrictions are imposed on them in many countries, and in our country there is a high level of falsification, the main reasons for which are: the profitability and profitability of the sale of such products , the impunity of the counterfeiter, the desire of product purchasing organizations to buy cheap counterfeit non-alcoholic beverages in order to make undeserved profits, the ineffectiveness of control mechanisms, the absence of persons responsible for quality in trade organizations, which, hopefully, will receive due attention.

Based on the presented material, we once again emphasize the safety of consumption of natural fruit and vegetable juices for human health compared to non-alcoholic soft drinks and recommend their mass consumption.

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Four-wheeled tractor with functional front axle

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On the issue of creating a highly maneuverable 4-wheeled tractor for cotton growing

One of the main works of LLC "Design and Technological Center of Agricultural Engineering" (LLC "DTCAE") is currently a project to create a new highly maneuverable specialized 4-wheel tractor designed for the cultivation of cotton and other high-stemmed crops.

The purpose of this project is to create an industrial model of a highly maneuverable high-speed 4-wheel tractor with the possibility of turning on the spot in the field. The use of such a machine will increase the return of cotton fields by significantly reducing the destruction of plants on the turning lanes during turns of the machine-tractor unit, reducing the alienation of agricultural land to the turning lanes, reducing soil compaction when using a tractor with a 4x2 wheel formula (four-wheeled with two driving wheels), increasing productivity due to the possibility of using a new tractor 6-and and 8-row agricultural machines, increasing stability, straightness of movement and controllability of the tractor.

The fundamental design difference of the new tractor from the currently mass - produced ones is the introduction of the following innovations into its design:

- in the front axle – a special design of the control mechanism of the front guide wheels, allowing them to be deployed in different directions.
- in the transmission – a hydrodynamic turning mechanism (HDTM) that allows the rear driving wheels to rotate in different directions with the same angular velocity to ensure the tractor turns in place around the vertical axis passing through the center of the rear axle;

The simultaneous operation of these two systems allows the tractor to turn in place around a vertical axis passing through the middle of the axis of the rear drive axle of the tractor.

Below is a description of the design of the tractor's front axle control mechanism, which provides a turn of the controlled wheels in opposite directions.

The design of this option is shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1.

Figure 1.

The amount of movement of the semi-rods is limited by the stroke length of the piston of the hydraulic cylinders. After the pistons of the hydraulic cylinders have worked out their stroke, the half-rods are blocked into a single thrust by hydraulic locks. The length of the blocked half-rod is equal to the sum of the displacements of the two half-rods, i.e., the sum of the stroke lengths of the hydraulic cylinder pistons. In the side turn mode (turning the tractor on the spot), the working fluid is supplied through the distributor and through the hydraulic locks to the piston cavities of the hydraulic cylinders 3. This opens the valves of the hydraulic locks 4. The rod cavities of the hydraulic cylinders 3, the piston cavities of the hydraulic cylinders of rotation 5 are connected to the drain. As a result of this, half thrusts are unlocked. Under the action of the pressure of the liquid entering the piston cavities of the hydraulic cylinders, the pistons extend the rods and push apart the half-rods connected to them. Through the levers 6, the half-rods turn the rotary shafts 7 mounted on them with forks with wheels. The amount of movement of the semi-rods corresponds to the rotation of the wheels by 70° and is limited by the length of the piston stroke.

After turning the tractor in place, the hydraulic control system of the turning mechanism leads the transverse thrust to the position corresponding to the transport and working mode of the tractor.

To turn the tractor on the spot, especially against the background of plowing, additional traction is required. To obtain additional traction, it was decided to activate the rear axle during the turn. At the same time, when turning the tractor in place, the rear wheels should rotate in different directions, creating additional traction in the direction of rotation.

To implement the proposed method of rotation, a hydraulic differential rotation mechanism (HDTM) has been developed, shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Hydraulic differential turning mechanism (HDTM):

1, 3 – gear wheels; 2 – shaft; 4 – hub; 5 – driver; 6 – satellites; 7 – satellite axis; 8 – hydraulic motor;
9 – spool mechanism; 10 – crown gear; 11 – solar gear.

HDTM consists of a shaft with two gears that are in constant engagement with the driven gears of the final drive, a planetary gearbox, a reversible planetary hydraulic motor and a spool mechanism.

One gear wheel is fixed on the shaft of the rotation mechanism. The outwardly protruding shaft shank, on the side of the first wheel, is a lateral synchronous power take-off shaft (PTO). On the opposite side of the shaft, a second gear wheel is installed, which rotates relative to the shaft on a plain bearing. The splined end of the gear wheel is connected through the crown gear to the hydraulic motor housing. The spline end of the gear is connected through the crown gear to the hydraulic motor housing. The spline end of the shaft, on the side of the free-seated wheel, is connected through the driver, satellite axes, satellites and a solar gear to the driveshaft of the hydraulic motor. A spool distribution mechanism is fixed on the outer end of the hydraulic motor with studs.

When driving in a straight line, the hydraulic motor controlled from the main distributor of the tractor is not switched on. At the same time, the gears and the semi-axles of the final gears are connected into a single rigid system, the differential is blocked.

When the hydraulic motor is turned on by the handle of the tractor's hydraulic distributor, the gears begin to rotate at different speeds, the tractor, accordingly, turns around one of the driving rear wheels.

When the parking brake is activated additionally, the tractor turns around the center of the rear axle axis, i.e., in place.

The design documentation for the revision of the hydraulic planetary motor (MHP 125) has been developed.

A construction documentation was developed for the spool mechanism, assembly of the MGP 125 with the spool mechanism and drawings of the hydraulic lines connecting them. In the planetary hydraulic motor 8 (Figure 3), the output shaft with a bearing support is eliminated, the cardan shaft is directly connected to the sun gear 11 of the planetary gearbox, a spool mechanism 9 is installed, the spool of which is rigidly connected to the hydraulic motor housing and the crown gear of the gearbox

10, with the ability to rotate as one, and the body is mounted on the spool with the ability to remain motionless.

The spool mechanism 9 is connected by two pressure-drain hydraulic lines with one of the hydraulic distributor sections of the tractor hydraulic system, and a drainage hydraulic line with the tractor oil tank. The working fluid under pressure flows through one of the hydraulic lines to the spool mechanism. Through the system of spool channels, the working fluid enters the chambers of variable volume of the hydraulic motor rotor, forcing it to orbit around the stator axis with some eccentricity, while simultaneously rotating around its own axis in the opposite direction of orbital movement, and from the chambers on the opposite side, where the volume is reduced, the spent the liquid is displaced by the teeth of the rotor through the channels of the spool mechanism into the drain hydraulic line. Through the cardan shaft of the hydraulic motor, sun gear 11, shaft 2, gear 1, one rear wheel of the tractor rotates in one direction. Through satellites 6, ring gear 10, gear 3, the other rear wheel of the tractor rotates in the opposite direction. With the proper setting of the front axle guide wheels (with a total angle of 180°), the tractor turns on the spot. When changing the direction of the supply of the working fluid to the HDTM using the tractor hydraulic distributor, the tractor turns in the opposite direction.

The tractor hydraulic system includes: a hydraulic pump, a hydraulic distributor, a metering pump with a priority valve, a hydraulic tank, a heat exchanger, hinged system hydraulic cylinders, pipelines and hydraulic fittings. Additionally, the tractor is equipped with: a hydraulic system for the drive of rotation and control of the steering wheels of the front axle, a hydrostatic differential rotation mechanism.

The hydraulic distributor is used in four sections: to ensure the operation of hydraulic systems of agricultural machines - 2 sections, for the rear hydraulic system - 1 section, for HDTM - 1 section.

Study of arsenic contamination of natural waters and soils of Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region

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Abstract. The study of arsenic contamination of rivers (Lukhuni and Tskhenistskali), artesian and spring waters, as well as soils in the areas adjacent to arsenic processing enterprises of the Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region, is discussed in the paper. In June 2022, the first fieldwork was carried out in Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region to solve the set tasks: natural water sampling points and soil sampling points were selected from the background, polluted and recreational areas at 0-5 and 5-20 cm soil depth. Samples were taken to determine arsenic in suspended particles.

The content of the total form of arsenic was determined in the collected water samples and soil samples.

Analyzes were carried out using modern methods and equipment that meet to international standards. Arsenic content has been detected in rivers, artesian and drinking waters, and soils.

Based on the determination of the arsenic concentration of surface, artesian, and drinking water, as well as soils, the following conclusions were made:

- In surface waters (Lukhuni and Tshnistskali) the hazard index is less than 1 ($HQ_{sw} < 1$) and they are not in danger;
- In artesian and drinking waters, the hazard index is greater than 1 ($HQ_{dw} > 1$), these waters are at risk;
- 10 soil samples at risk were identified, where the hazard index is greater than 1 ($HQ_s > 1$).

Key words: Pollution by Arsenic, surface water, artesian and drinking water, soils

Introduction

Arsenic is a natural component of the Earth's crust and is widespread in any ecosystem. It exists in nature as in organic and inorganic forms, and inorganic forms is very toxic [1]. Although arsenic can absorb the skin, and the respiratory tract, it

still mainly enters the human body from food and drinking water. Organic arsenic species are most often found in marine products, and terrestrial products are mostly inorganic forms of 3-5 valent arsenic. Therefore, arsenic enters the food chain mainly from contaminated soil and water [2, 3].

The study of Arsenic pollution is a priority issue in Georgia, where many natural or anthropogenic sources are present. In particular, in the region of Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti, where arsenic ores were mined, processed, and arsenic-containing compounds were produced for ten years. Today, both deposits are conserved and no arsenic is produced, but contaminated soils are still left for future generations. To this day, in the villages of Uravi and Tsana, on the territory of the Sam chemical factory, toxic waste from the Soviet period left over from the production of arsenic (more than 130 thousand tons containing 4-9% white arsenic, to which are added thousands of tons of arsenic-containing waste imported from Russia, including those left in the open air is stored) [4].

Over the years, the main mechanism for the spread of arsenic waste has been associated with the leaching and transport of toxic waste by atmospheric precipitation and flood waters. They accumulate in the soil, where soil contamination with arsenic significantly exceeds the norm [5-8]. In the oxidation zone, after a certain time, arsenic from waste sulfide ores and incinerators can be transferred to a mobile (soluble) form [9, 10], which is easily transported to plants and living organisms.

Often, arsenic is not fixed in river water, but it is present in suspended particles and bottom sediments. Increased arsenic content in bottom sediments compared to river water, in bottom sediments compared to river water can be explained by the high specific gravity of arsenic-bearing ores: 3.4-6.2 g/cm³ and their tendency to sedimentation, therefore it is appropriate to determine the arsenic concentration in them [9].

In addition, the Lukhuni and Tskhenistskali rivers are tributaries of the Rioni River, which is the main source of drinking water for the city of Kutaisi and is also used

for irrigation. At the same time, this region is one of the most important tourist regions of Georgia, which significantly determines the scale of the disaster.

Study area and methods

It is planned to study the arsenic contamination of the rivers (Lukhuni and Tskhenistskali), artesian and spring waters, as well as soils in the areas surrounding the arsenic processing enterprises of the Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti regions. In June 2022, the first fieldwork was carried out in Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region to address the tasks: natural water sampling points and soil sampling points were selected from the background, polluted and recreational areas at 0-5 and 5-20 cm soil depth. Samples were taken to determine arsenic in suspended particles.

The content of the common form of arsenic was determined in the collected water samples and soil samples [11, 12].

Analysis were carried out using modern methodologies and equipment that meet international standards, namely:

1. Plasma-emission spectrometer- ICP-OES; Epa method 200.8;
2. pH meter - Milwaukee-Mi 150.

Discussion of results

The obtained results (Tab. 1, Fig. 1) show that, arsenic concentrations are detected in the river waters (Lukhuni and Tskhenistskali Rivers), both in the background and in the samples taken below the contaminated area, although they do not exceed maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) in any of the cases. It should be noted that both rivers were flooded and turbid at the time of sampling.

There is a difference in the samples taken from the spring waters (Tab. 2, Fig. 1). In the spring water taken in the territory of Uravi 2 (150-200 m away), the arsenic content is almost equal to one, and in the spring water from the mountain to Tsana - arsenic the concentration is 0.0123 mg/l and its ratio to MPC is 1.2, the concentration of arsenic is 1.2 times higher than the maximum permissible concentration. It is worth noting that both these waters are intensively used for drinking by the population. The content of arsenic in the acidic spring water above Lentekhi is low

and its concentration is 0.0013 mg/l. The content of arsenic in the Shaori aquifer is also low (0.0096 mg/l).

Table 1. Arsenic content in the study Rivers - June 2022

#	Ingredient	Lukhuni Uravi upper	Lukhuni (100 meters below the sarcophagus)	Tskhenistskali Tsana upper	Tskhenistskali Lentekhi below	Shaori reservoir	MPC
1	Arsenic-As, mg/l	0.0035	0.0111	0.0056	0.0017	0.0096	0.05

Figure 1. Arsenic content in research Rivers, artesian and drinking waters

Table 2. Arsenic content in artesian and drinking waters, June 2022

#	Ingredient	Spring water in the territory of Uravi 2 (150-200m away)	Spring water from the mountain, in the direction of Tsana	Acidic water (source) Lentekhi upper	MPC
1	Arsenic -As, mg/l	0.0097	0.0123/1.2	0.0013	0,01 0.01

The ratio of arsenic concentration to MPC is given in the denominator.

The risk assessment step provides a comparison of the measured concentration levels of arsenic to the Environmental Quality Standards for particular media (surface

water, drinking water). This comparison provides the risk estimation following the equation defined below [13]:

$$\text{Hazard index (HQ)} = \text{Measured concentration (MC)} / \text{EQS}_{\text{SW, DW, Soil}}$$

In case $\text{HQ} > 1.0$, arsenic is considered as a potential risk for the environment and health risk for the population.

The following EQS or Guidelines limit values will be used:

- Drinking water - 0.01 mg/l (maximum permissible concentrations in Georgia on the approval of the technical regulations for the protection of drinking water pollution, Resolution No. 58) [14].
- Surface water - 0.05 mg/l (maximum permissible concentrations on the approval of the technical regulations for the protection of surface water pollution of Georgia, (Government of Georgia Resolution No. 425) [15].
- Soil - 2.0 mg/kg (maximum concentrations on the approval of the technical regulations for the protection of surface waters of Georgia, Resolution No. 297/N) [16].

Table 3. Arsenic content in the river suspended particles, June, 2022

#	Sampling location	coordinates	Results mg/kg
1 1	Lukhuni river - 100 m below the sarcophagus	X- 358975 Y- 4721438	19.29
2 2	Tskhenistskali river - below Lentekhi	X- 313988 Y- 4737237	14.03

Arsenic can be seen from the third table, the total content of Arsenic in the river suspended particles is quite high: in about 100 m below the river Lukhuni-Sarkophagus - 19.29 mg/kg, and below the river Tskhenistskali-Lentekhi - 14.03

mg/kg. Since sampling from the rivers took place during the flood period of the rivers, it was not possible to collect bottom sediments.

Table 4. Arsenic content in soil samples

10.06.2022

#	Sampling location	coordinates	Analysis results mg/kg	Hazard index
1	Village Sori 0-5 cm	X- 358540	9.79	4,99
1	“-----” 5-20 cm	Y- 4714028	15.02	7,51
2	Utsera 0- 5 cm	X- 380725	29.99	15,00
2	“-----” 5-20 cm	Y- 4721383	21.88	10,94
3	Oni 0- 5 cm	X- 373067	17.57	8,79
3	“-----” 5-20 cm	Y- 4717199	13.57	6,79
4	Village Abari 0-5 cm	X- 357647	2.77	1,39
4	“-----” 5-20 cm	Y- 4719592	14.08	7,04
5	Nickortsminda 0-5 cm	X- 341836	7.79	3,90
5	“-----” 5-20 cm	Y- 4702232	17.44	8,72
6	Shore of Lake Shaori 0-5 cm	X- 340808	16.58	8,29
6	“-----” 5-20 cm	Y- 4699495	8.56	4,28
7	Tskhenistskali beach, Lentekhi 0-5 cm	X- 313992	13.26	6,63
7	“-----” 5-20 cm	Y- 4737247	32.03	16,02
8	Uravi N1 (before) 0-5 cm	X- 359938	71.97	35,99
8	“-----” 5-20 cm	Y- 4723063	32.85	16,43

9	Uravi-2	0-	X-		
9	5 cm		359728	63.76	31,88
9	“-----”		Y-		
	5-20 cm		4722088	20.31	10,16
1	Village	Likheti	X-		
0	0-5 cm		356025	24.17	12,09
1	“-----”		Y-		
1	5-20 cm		4718134	16.62	8,31
0					

Arsenic can be seen in the fourth table, soil samples were taken from agricultural areas (village of Sori, village of Abari, Lentekhi-Tskhenistskali beach, before Uravi N1 (Kakala area), 50 m from Uravi-2, village of Likheti near the school); From recreational (Nikortsminda, coast of Shaori reservoir) and background (Utsera, Oni) places. Soil samples were taken at 0-5 cm and 5-20 cm depth.

The obtained results show that the content of the common form of arsenic in the soil samples taken from agricultural fields (Sori, Abari and Likheti villages) is relatively less and amounts are the following: 9.97/4.99 and 15.02/7.51; 2.77/1.39 and 14.08/7.04; 24.17/12.09 and 16.62/8.31 mg/kg - at 0-5 and 5-20 cm depth. The numerator shows the arsenic content in the samples, and the denominator shows the hazard index. It should be noted that the content of arsenic in the upper layer of the soil (0-5 cm) is higher compared to the depth (5-20 cm).

The arsenic content in the areas affected by the Uravi and Tsana arsenic factories is much higher. In particular, the arsenic content before Uravi-1 (Kakala district) is 71.97/35.99 and 32.85/16.43 mg/kg at a depth of 5-20 cm; 50 m from Uravi-2 - 63.76/31.88 and 20.31/10.16 mg/kg, and Lentekhi on Tskhenistskali river beach - 13.26/6.63 and 32.03/16.02 mg/kg respectively.

The content of arsenic in the soil is lower in the recreation area compared to the agricultural fields, which is confirmed by the data of the analysis. The concentration of arsenic in Nikortsminda and Shaori reservoir coasts is 7.79/3.90 and 17.44/8.72; 16.58/8.29 and 8.56/4.28 mg/kg at 0-5 cm and 5-20 cm depth.

In soil samples taken from the background area - Oni and Utsera, the content of arsenic at the depth of 0-5 and 5-20 cm is 17.57/8.79 and 13.57/6.79 mg/kg;

29.99/15.00 and 21.88/10.94 mg/kg respectively. Such high arsenic concentrations in background location may be due to the natural presence of arsenic in the soil.

Thus, the content of arsenic in soil samples taken from agricultural, recreational, and background areas has been detected.

In the soil samples taken from agricultural fields, the content of the common form of arsenic in the villages of Sori, Abari and Likheti is relatively less, and accordingly, the hazard index is: 4.99 and 7.51; 1.39 and 7.04; 12.09 and 8.31 respectively at 0-5 and 5-20 cm depth. It should be noted that the content of arsenic in the upper layer of the soil (0-5 cm) is higher compared to the depth (5-20 cm).

The arsenic content in the areas affected by the Uravi and Tsana arsenic factories is much higher. In particular, the hazard index before Uravi-1 (Kakala district) at a depth of 0-5 cm is 35.99 and at a depth of 5-20 cm it is 16.43; in 50 m from Uravi-2 at a depth of 0-5 cm - 31.88 and at a depth of 5-20 cm - 10.16; and on Lentekhi-Tskhenistskali river coast - 6.63 and - 16.02 respectively. Thus, the areas surrounding Uravi-1 and Uravi-2 are the most polluted with arsenic.

Arsenic content is relatively less in the agricultural fields, in the villages of Sori, Abari and Likheti.

The content of arsenic in the soil in the recreation area is even less compared to the agricultural fields, which is confirmed by the data of the analysis. The hazard index in the coastline of Nikortsminda and Shaori reservoirs is 3.90 and 8.72, respectively; 8.29 and 4.28 at 0-5 and 5-20 cm depth.

In the soil samples taken from the background site - Oni and Utsera, the hazard index is 8.79 and 6.79, respectively; 15.00 and 10.94 at the depth of 0-5 and 5-20 cm. At background location, such high arsenic concentrations may be due to the natural presence of arsenic in the soil.

Conclusion

Based on the determination of the arsenic concentration of surface, artesian, and drinking water, as well as soils, the following conclusions were made:

- In surface waters (Lukhuni and Tshnistskali) the hazard index is less than 1 ($HQ_{sw} < 1$) and they are not in danger;

- In artesian and drinking waters, the hazard index is greater than 1 (HQ_{dw} >1), these waters are at risk;
- 10 soil samples at risk were identified, where the hazard index is greater than 1 (HQ_s >1).

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ECONOMY

The management system of JSC “Railways of Uzbekistan” and the relevance of its optimization

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Annotation. This concept shows that a number of systemic problems and shortcomings remain that impede the successful implementation of state policy on the modernization of economic sectors. In particular, it was noted that the level of implementation of modern innovative methods of planning and organizing work into the management process does not allow for the effective implementation of decisions and operational control over its progress, and also causes excessive bureaucratization and high costs in state and economic management bodies.

Key words: large-scale reforms, implementing project, determined, mechanisms, focuses on the development, entrusted, practical point.

The concept of “New Uzbekistan” put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev gave impetus to further escalation of large-scale reform processes carried out at the present stage of development of our country. The idea “Building a new state of Uzbekistan”¹, first voiced by the President of the Republic on September 29, 2017, has become the ideological basis for improving the activities of state and economic management in our country.

The issue of improving the activities of state and economic management bodies, which is mentioned in the “New Strategy of Uzbekistan” based on this idea “Increasing labor productivity by at least 2 times”², involves large-scale reforms. These reforms require the improvement of modern management methods, including mechanisms for introducing project management systems into the activities of

¹ Festive congratulations of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to teachers and mentors of Uzbekistan. President.uz/uz/lists/view/1088

² The Movement of Entrepreneurs and Business People - Speech at the 10th Congress of the Liberal Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, held on September 9, 2021.

manufacturing and service enterprises in order to improve state and economic management bodies.

The fact that the implementation of the project management system in our country was marked by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan means that this issue has been raised to the level of state policy, and this research work on the topic “Improving the mechanisms for implementing project management in the activities of enterprises” is relevant. The study of the issue of improving project management mechanisms on the example of “Uzbekistan Railways” JSC is significant in that it focuses on the development of a new management model aimed at fundamentally improving the company's management system.

The fact that Sh.M. Mirziyoyev was determined to improve management from the first period of his appointment to the post of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan determines the important tasks of implementing administrative reform in this regard, as well as the prospect and need for administrative reform³.

In order to eliminate systematic errors in this direction, the National Project Management Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was created, the main task of which was to introduce a project management system in our country⁴. In this regard, the agency has achieved a number of results. In particular, knowledge of project management standards was collected and the knowledge of employees of state and economic control bodies was increased, as well as a system for training specialists based on this specialization was established.

However, the agency has not yet been able to fully resolve the issue of introducing a project management system into the activities of state and economic management bodies, which is the main mission entrusted to it. It is for this reason that this research work on the topic “Improving the mechanisms for implementing

³ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 8, 2017 No. PF-5185 “On approval of the concept of administrative reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan”

⁴ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 24, 2017 No. PF-5120 “On measures to introduce a project management system in the Republic of Uzbekistan”

project management in the activities of an enterprise (on the example of “Uzbekistan Railways” JSC)” is relevant both from a scientific and practical point of view.

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The importance of recreational activities in the development of ecological tourism

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Annotation

The paper discusses the importance of ecotourism as a basis for sustainable development. The capacity of using the territories by ecotourists is also presented. By calculating the recreational possibilities of the area, it becomes possible to calculate the number of visitors that is safe for protected areas. The calculation of recreational opportunities of tourist facilities allows to manage the use of resources and to determine the needs of infrastructure development of the system. Indicators of recreational opportunities also reflect the quantitatively expressed ability of the object to provide human psycho-physiological comfort.

Key words: ecotourism, capacity, recreational load

Introduction

Ecotourism is considered the basis of sustainable development of tourism. Ecosystem preservation and sustainable use of natural resources are important to meet the demands of both current and future generations. Ecological tourism is one of the important elements of the development of sustainable tourism. The deterioration of the ecological situation in the world was caused by such factors as environmental pollution, ozone depletion, climate change, reduction of biodiversity, shortage of drinking water, changes in natural processes in the biosphere.

Therefore, more and more importance is given to promoting the development of ecological tourism. But the degree of utilization of the environment by ecotourists

is also quite high, therefore it is necessary to introduce ethical norms of behavior in the natural environment. It is necessary to consider the marginal load of the use of the territories by ecotourists and to calculate the recreational possibilities of the territory. This will allow us to calculate the number of visitors that are safe for protected areas. By calculating the recreational opportunities of tourist facilities, you can manage the use of resources and determine the needs of the infrastructure development of the system.

The purpose of the article is to discuss and analyze ecotourism as the basis of sustainable development of tourism, for this the main ways of calculating capacity and "limit load" on ecotourist paths were studied.

Ecotourism as the basis of sustainable development of tourism

Ecological tourism appears as a tool for sustainable development of territories. The definition of this concept has been proposed by various authors and organizations, including: World Tourism Organization (UNWTO, 1994), International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUNC, 1996), International Ecotourism Society (TIES, 1991).

The concept of ecological tourism is based on the following principles:

- getting to know the nature, local customs and culture of the visited areas;
- Minimizing the negative impact on the natural landscapes and socio-cultural communities of the visited areas;
- Promotion of protection of nature and local socio-cultural environment;
- environmental education of participants in ecotourism (local population and tourists);
- Economic efficiency and contribution to the sustainable development of the visited regions.

Sustainable development is a process of change in which the exploitation of resources, the direction of investments, the orientation of scientific and technological development, and institutional changes converge and strengthen existing and future capacities to meet people's needs and aspirations. The concept of sustainable development implies the use of three approaches: economic, social and

environmental (UN Conference on Environment and Development, Rio de Janeiro, 1992). The economic approach to the concept of sustainable development is based on the Hicks-Lyndale theory of maximum income flow (optimal use of limited resources and use of environmentally friendly resources). The economic approach to the concept of sustainable development is based on the Hicks-Lyndale theory of maximum income flow (optimal use of limited resources and use of environmentally friendly resources). The social component of sustainable development is human-centered and aims to maintain the stability of social and cultural systems, including reducing the number of destructive conflicts between people. From an ecological point of view, sustainable development must ensure the integrity of biological and physical natural systems. including reducing the number of destructive conflicts between people. It is desirable to preserve cultural capital and diversity on a global scale, as well as to make fuller use of sustainable development practices in non-dominant cultures. From an ecological point of view, sustainable development must ensure the integrity of biological and physical natural systems. The social component of sustainable development is human-centered and aims to maintain the stability of social and cultural systems, including reducing the number of destructive conflicts between people. It is also desirable to preserve cultural capital and diversity on a global scale, as well as to make fuller use of sustainable development practices in non-dominant cultures.

The main principle of sustainable tourism is to limit the volume of tourism development or tourist flows in tourist destinations, for which it is necessary to determine the capacity and use limiting factors.

Basic ways of calculating bandwidth and "limit load"

"Throughput" is the level of use of the territory by visitors, which ensures a high level of their satisfaction with a negligible impact on resources.

A proper planning and management approach to national parks should determine the optimal level of recreational use of the park. Recreational capacity is an important concept in the management of protected areas, which must be reflected in the strategic development plan of protected areas.

A proper planning and management approach to national parks should determine the optimal level of recreational use of the park. Recreational capacity is an important concept in the management of protected areas, which must be reflected in the strategic development plan of protected areas.

Traditionally, recreational load calculations take into account the simultaneous presence of a certain number of people in a natural area, breaking ground cover, building trails, and setting up tent camps.

If we know the recreational opportunities of the areas and the average duration of visitors, we can determine the annual recreational opportunities using the formula:

$$P_{\text{year}} = P_{\text{day}} \times T$$

On the other hand, the recreational opportunities of the territory during one working day are determined by the formula:

Where: P_{day} – recreational opportunities of the territory during one working day, T – accounting period (equal to the average number of working days per year in the calculation period 248 working days).

On the other hand, the recreational opportunities of the territory during one working day are determined by the formula:

$$P_{\text{day}} = \frac{t_Y}{t_M} \times P_{\text{std}}$$

where: t_Y – accounting period time (8 hours)

t_M – average duration of the route (4.5 hours),

P_{std} – the standard value is determined by the area.

Using the proposed formulas, such indicators as the recreational possibilities of the territory (excursion zones) during one working day and one year were determined.

We interviewed the employees of the visitor centers of Vashlovani and Algeti national parks and the number of visitors to the mentioned parks in the seasonal period is about 67 per day. The results show that the actual average park visitation is lower than the capacity of the routes on the parks, however, these are average

numbers. In practice, there is still a risk of overcrowding, especially during peak seasons. Since park visits and trail use are subject to season, weather, and trail conditions. Therefore, the management system should be developed by integrating the new track system. It is also necessary to take into account the fact that different ecosystems react differently to the loads, as well as the seasonality factor, for example: May, June, July, August are seasonally active periods.

If we take into account the scientist V. According to Dezhkin's research, tourist trails through mossy forests can withstand loads of up to 25 people/ha without significant damage, while pine trails can withstand up to 15 people/ha. For birch and mixed forests

higher permissible load - 50 people ha; on moraine plains and 35 person/ha.

Nevertheless, there is no unified approach to adjusting the general norms for determining permissible loads on landscapes in relation to their individual properties, since in the processes of natural age development, forests and other ecosystems undergo certain changes, which are characterized by the natural variability of their constituent components.

The study of recreational opportunities is carried out by the number of visitors per 1 ha area for 1 hour. When there are more than 100 people/ha in the forest environment, the balance is disturbed. Broader restrictions should be imposed in these areas

In order to reduce recreational impacts on landscapes. [4, p. 15]

Based on the above, we have calculated the recreational opportunities of the tourist route of the "Kingdom Ridge" of the protected area of Algeti, in the event that a 16-kilometer section of the circular route receives 67 people per day, where the trip is carried out in a forested environment, the overload rate will be permissible, and the annual norm of visitors should be 16 600 visitors.

Nevertheless, in Georgia, there is currently no unified approach, terminology, qualitative and quantitative criteria that will make it possible to determine the fact that the maximum load has been reached in the recreation area, there is no unified

methodological approach and organizational-economic mechanism that will regulate the load on tourist and health facilities and in protected areas.[3]

In the case of a critical limit of conductivity, there will be negative effects on the local population and the environment, so it is necessary to develop strategic management directions, namely:

- increasing the conduction potential;
- equal distribution of visitors;
- Travel restriction

The scientific approach of sustainable tourism has been studied by many scientists, we have studied and discussed the conceptual vision of the American scientist Jafar Jafar, who gave us the "platform" model, where he proposed the evolution of tourism research.

J. Jafar's platform model provides a useful framework for understanding how tourism can cause harm as well as benefit, and has transformed the approach from the promotion of mass tourism to the realization that there is a need to develop conservation-oriented tourism, sustainable tourism. He gave us a platform, each step of which is based on the previous one. According to Jafar, these platforms are:

Propaganda	The period after World War II	Tourism has protected the principles of environmental protection and cultural traditions, provided employment, stimulated the economy, facilitated intercultural communication and even established world peace. It promoted intercultural communication and even the establishment of world peace.
Warning	1970 year	The services provided by tourism are seasonal and low-wage, development can lead to cash outflows from communities, commercialization of

		culture, and negative environmental impacts.
adaptable	1980year	Both of the above approaches are valuable and tourism development can be beneficial if it is focused on the host community, reducing negative impacts and improving communication between hosts and visitors.
based on knowledge	1990 year	Tourism development is a system that has many impacts and benefits that can be implemented in different directions, and that is why it should be considered together.

Jafar's platform studies were ultimately based on the need to create a sustainable tourism model, which many scholars agreed with. Scientist Schafer notes that: sustainable tourism development is the basis for establishing harmony between stakeholder groups to a certain level and achieving the desired level of quality of life in the long term.[4]

There are the following links between ecotourism and sustainable development:

- **Awareness:** Tourism enables visitors and local residents to learn about environmental issues and cross-cultural differences, thereby changing their attitudes towards sustainability issues not only during travel but also in their daily lives.
- **Dependency:** Tourism is based on the needs of visitors who are focused on the search for a pristine and clean environment that exists on its own history and cultural traditions.
- **Interaction:** Tourism as a service sector is based on the introduction of new destinations, which means generating direct and indirect funds through the interaction between visitors, the local community and the environment.

Unfortunately, when drawing up tourist routes in nature, such concepts as the stability of the natural territorial complex (a certain limit of recreational load) and

the recreational capacity of the territory (the maximum, taking into account the types of recreation, the number of people who can be in the territory at the same time without causing degradation of biogeocenosis and psychological discomfort). As a result of unregulated use, ecosystems are degraded and their use as tourism objects becomes impossible. In such conditions, only momentary income can be talked about, and the economic efficiency of these enterprises is highly doubtful.

Conclusion:

1. Sustainable development is a process that includes ecological, economic and social aspects of tourism development, and in order to achieve long-term sustainability, it is necessary to balance all three directions;
2. Jafar Jafar's platform model creates a useful framework for understanding why it became necessary to establish sustainable tourism, because the mentioned model gives us the condition that incorrectly planned tourism can cause harm to society along with benefits;
3. Calculating the carrying capacity will allow us to determine the rate of recreational use, which will make it possible to identify the capacity of protected areas to receive tourists and to determine the number of people who will cause minimal damage to protected areas.

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